

Revisiting the Political Will in Educational Development: The Case of Cameroon

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Abstract

This paper sets out to inquire whether the political will enhances or obstructs educational development in Cameroon. The problem identified here is that policy making is one reality and follow-up and implementation is another. The central arguments in this paper have been articulated within the context of political science theories like the Marxist conflict theory, John Rawls theory of justice, John Dewey's theory of democratic education, Rousseau's social contract theory and James Banks' multicultural education theory. Both qualitative and quantitative methods of research have been used in this study. Questionnaires, interviews and focus group discussions and participant observation constituted the research instruments. A thematic analysis supported by descriptive statistics was used to present and discuss the facts studied. This research questions the fairness in policy-making and wonders whether the political will follows the right procedures to enact relevant policies for educational growth. Findings prove that there is more to be desired as far as policy making and implementation of the policies in Cameroon is concerned. This paper concludes that in order to ensure fairness and quality in the provision of educational values, the political will has to be strong as far as justice, fairness and the provision of educational opportunities is concerned in Cameroon.

Key words; *Political will; Educational development; and Cameroon.*

Introduction

Most often differences that arise between cultures, linguistic differences, ethnic groups, regions, philosophies tend to compromise the process of peace, tolerance and educational growth. This situation is very particular between Anglophones and Francophones in Cameroon. The politics of regional balance seem to fuel problems between the two sub-systems of education because one group put forth arguments and proofs of marginalisation in several spheres of life. The genesis of the problem can be traced in the defeat of Germany in the first world war. The German annexation of Cameroon took place in 1884 and with the defeat of the Germans in the First World War, Cameroon was divided by Britain and France and later placed as a mandated territory under these two colonial powers (Fonkeng, 2007). The colonial powers administered this territory with their respective cultures and this explains the bicultural nature of the country. At the moment, the two colonial regions administered by Britain and France as oversea territories are referred to as the Anglophone and Francophone regions of Cameroon respectively. This colonial biculture presents a bicultural school system known as the Anglosaxon and the French sub-systems of education (Ngalim, 2014c).

Consequently, there are principally two sub-systems of education following the bicultural nature of Cameroon. These include the French and the English Sub-systems. In the French sub-system, the certificates obtained are *Certificat d'Eleve du Premier*, *Brevet d'Etudes du Premier Cycle*, *Probatoire* and *Baccalaureat* respectively. On the other hand, in the English sub-system, the certificates obtained include the First School Leaving Certificate and the Ordinary and Advanced Levels. In both sub-systems, technical secondary schools exist where students can obtain an alternative education to generally and academically oriented programmes. The technical educational programmes are also carried out for seven years for students between the ages of twelve and nineteen. For technical secondary schools, students pursue formal education, which lead to the end degree of City and Guilds Part III or technical General Certificate of Education (GCE), Ordinary and Advanced Levels, which also permit students to further to universities or technical higher educational institutes. In the French speaking technical High schools, the educational programme prepares students for work or for further studies upon completion. The certificates obtained for the first and second cycles include *Brevet de Technicien* and *Baccalaureat Technique* qualifying students to pursue careers or study further in higher institutions.

Within this background, there are some antagonisms between the values of the francophones and those of the anglophones. Given that the Francophones constitute the majority, some schools of thought maintain that policy-making in education tend to favour and privilege francophones to the relative neglect of Anglophones. In this light, the political will betrays the marginalisation of Anglophones and also the fact that the francophone culture has the monopoly of truth. The Anglophones whose values are marginalised tend to react to assert and emphasize their place in the country. At times, inappropriate means of expressing grievances arise because there is seemingly no one to entertain dialogue and look into the matter (Nieto, 1992 ; Sobol, 1990 ; Banks 1989). In Aristotle's political philosophy, it is the responsibility of every state to protect the autonomy and rights of everyone in education (Copleston, 1962). In case of grievances, the state has to take measures towards an amicable dialogue in solving problems. Cameroon is characterised by differences and one has to be tolerant to accept other ways of perceiving truth. Considering the argument against the universality of cultural norms, there is a need to emphasize pluralism, diversity or differences as a means of living in communion (Bennett, 1990). In democratic education, John Dewey argues that education is the only means through which we can establish the type of society we want to have. If we want a society of solidarity irrespective of differences, then our education has to provide values that enhance solidarity in diversity, unity in difference. The issue at stake is to investigate whether the diversity of colonial cultures that bring forth problems of educational development in Cameroon can be traced in the political will.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study seeks to investigate whether the problems of educational development in Cameroon can be traced in the political will. Here, it is the question of determining the reliability of policies in educational matters. If the policies are bad, it will be impossible to implement them.

Specifically,

This study inquires whether the political will fosters policies that lead to the domination of the French sub-system over the English sub-system. The political will needs to implement policies that foster provision of human resource personnel to provide equal learning opportunities in the two sub-systems of education.

Also, to find out if the reaction of the political will to the division amongst Cameroonians on the subject of harmonisation of educational values compromise the politics of unity and national integration.

Research Questions

The main research question is; can problems of education be attributed to the political will?

- Does the political will foster policies that lead to the domination of the English sub-system by the French sub-system in Cameroon?
- Does the reaction of the political will to division of Cameroonians on harmonisation of educational values betray failure towards the politics of unity and national integration?

Hypothesis

The main hypothesis of this study holds that the political will is responsible for some of the problems of education in Cameroon.

Specifically;

- The absence of a strong political is responsible for the slow pace of providing equal learning opportunities and the domination of the English sub-system by the French sub-system.
- The division amongst Cameroonians on harmonisation of educational values betrays the weakness of policy making in enacting feasible educational policies to enhance unity and national integration.

Significance of the study

The absence of a strong political will renders policy-making theoretical. A major contemporary theory of education in Cameroon is the harmonisation of the sub-systems. The result of this process entails some common curricular values in the two sub-systems leading to similar elements in the syllabi and schemes of work. This educational politics has not yet attained its objectives even in basic education where

the number of years for learning has been harmonised. The number of years is the same in the secondary schools but the two sub-systems are not having basic common curricular values and structure. Harmonisation in educational politics entails the provision of equal learning opportunities with some similarities in curricular values, elaborated in the syllabi and schemes of work in the two official languages. This has to be done from the pre-primary, primary, secondary and high schools. With harmonisation, the problem of equity and quality hardly arises. Education is about fairness; therefore, all citizens in the same country, competing in the same platform should be given equal opportunities of learning and development (Ngalim, 2014c). This approach minimizes differences and provides a framework for policies that lead to unity and national integration in Cameroon.

Review of Related Literature

This review will be presented in two aspects: the conceptual and theoretical frameworks. Clarification of concepts like political will, policy-making, educational development, Cameroon, Anglophones and Francophones is imperative. For the theoretical framework, we shall exploit theories, multicultural theory of James Banks, democratic education theory of Dewey, the conflict theory of Karl Marx and the social contract theory of Jean Jacques Rousseau.

Conceptual Framework

The explanation of concepts like the political will, policy-making, Cameroon, educational development, Anglophones and Francophones enables us to present our arguments with little or no ambiguities. The political will in this context refers to the ability of those governing the state to enact policies and legal frameworks for education. The ability to implement the policy determines the strength of the political will. Bad and unfeasible policies betray the weakness of the political will (Ngalim, 2014c). Policy-making is the process that is employed by the governing body to enact legal frameworks and ideas that are binding in the management of the educational affairs of a nation.

Educational development refers to a sustained process of growth in the values of education which provide equal learning opportunities and privileges to persons irrespective of linguistic and cultural difference (Reboul, 1989). In this context, the provision of education opportunities are done irrespective of the type of sub-system of education (Ngalim, 2014b).

Talking of Cameroon, one is referring to a country in central Africa, with the history of three colonial powers of which the last two Britain and France who took over from the Germans after the First World War form the basis of the cultural controversy in education. This country is made up of Anglophones and Francophones following the English and the French cultures respectively. Literally speaking, Anglophone comes from two Greek words, *Anglo* means English and *Phone* means sound. An Anglophone in the literal sense is one who makes an English sound. In this perspective, considering *franco* as French, a Francophone is one who makes a French sound. This literal meaning explains the ambiguity of these identities created by some misguided anthropologists in Cameroon. With the fact that many francophones send their children to the English sub-system of education, many of them argue that these children who speak English and with certificates from the English system are therefore Anglophones. This approach is also used to explain the identity of Francophones. This is very misleading because the History of Cameroon cannot be explained in these terms. There is a geographical delimitation to the meaning of Anglophones and Francophones in Cameroon. It is only with the recognition of this geographical delimitation as explained in Cameroon history that one can unerringly assign identities of Anglophones and Francophones in Cameroon.

Theoretical Frameworks

Having examined the main concepts in this paper, it will be important to consider the theories that are used to justify the variables in the study. In the first place, we refer to the multicultural theory of James Banks. Multicultural education enhances peace and good citizenship between persons from pluralistic societies. There are many activities that could be employed to empower persons from different cultures, groups, linguistic origin, social class and colonial heritage. This permits the development of everyone's potential to let their full integration into the life of the community. Multicultural education promotes a study of one's values and the values of others in order to be open and tolerant to other experiences (Banks, 1989 ; Parker, 2003).

With Dewey's innovation of the democratic theory of education, one finds a theoretical framework that perpetuates values of multiculturalism. Democratic education refers to an educational approach which ensures that all learners have equal access to learning opportunities and privileges irrespective of age, sex, region, race, language, tribe, religion, country and colour. Democratic education and equity refer to fairness in the provision of educational facilities and values in order to permit individuals participate in the life of the community (Dewey, 1966:81 ; Reboul, 1989 ; Langwa & Ngalim, 2015). In the Cameroonian context, being an Anglophone or a Francophone should not be a reason for inclusion or exclusion from some privileges and rights. Equity refers to the provision of equal access and opportunities to all irrespective of socio-economic and cultural backgrounds. Equity frowns on all forms of discrimination and marginalisation. The socio-economic, cultural and political causes of lack of equity are to be deconstructed by multicultural education (Nelson, Palonsky & McCarthy, 2006 p.81).

The conflict theory of Karl Marx is exploited in this paper to explain the necessary antagonism that exist between people from different school sub-systems, backgrounds, languages, regions and tribes. With this theory, there are basically two basic classes; viz the haves in a capitalist context (the bourgeoisie) and the haves-not (proletariat). The relationship between these two classes rest upon a fundamental contradiction, where the bourgeoisie exploit the economic condition of the capitalist system to continuously exploit the proletariat who perpetually live at the subsistence level. While the bourgeoisie continue to grow rich through the exploitation of the poor, the proletariat remain poor. This class conflict caused by the contradiction of surplus value forces a dialectic movement to the next stage of history- socialism or communism (Stumpf & Fieser, 2003 ; Ngalim, 2014b). In the context of Cameroon in particular, the contradiction of different sub-systems of education with different colonial cultures has to undergo a synthesis in a common vision of a people who want to forge together. Diversity is not the basis for contradiction, but it is simply the different aspects of the same whole. Solidarity in diversity can be attained where the necessary processes of justice and peace are put in place. There is no need for superiority - inferiority complex. Numbers do not constitute the basis for truth. No sub-system of education is superior to the other whether it is the system of the majority or not (Ngalim, 2014b).

Following the social contract theory, a contract refers to an agreement between two equals. Equality here refers to the availability of the same opportunities, privileges and resources to all parties (Rawls, 1999). The principle of fairness requires the recognition of the contracting parties and the respect of the terms of the contract as stated at the time of the contract. This contract needs to be one of the steps towards harmonization in educational politics. Prior to harmonisation, the terms of the contract should be clearly spelt out. This contract must be revocable in case one of the contracting parties fails to keep to the terms (Rousseau, 1947). The revocability of the contract is a means of restoring confidence and trust in skeptics and cynics as regards the harmonisation process. Before this contract, it is necessary to sensitize Cameroonians on what the process entails. This is to deconstruct the fear of change, domination and assimilation. For this contract to be successful, an impartial arbiter needs to define the terms of the agreements and how it is to be managed. One of the terms has to define the status of each sub-system and what has to be harmonised. In this case, what are the values to synthesize and which ones remain in each sub-system? For example, the medium of communication has to be maintained. The organisation of the curriculum needs to promote the needs, experiences and aptitudes of all Cameroonians. Equal opportunities to learning indicate equitable distribution of educational facilities following the needs of the population (Reboul, 1989).

Finally, the contracting parties have to preserve the diversity of the Cameroonian culture because this is the basis on which the value of the curriculum is founded. The right accorded to each sub-system has to be presented with clarity and precision. Respect for these rights has to extend to decision-making. The provision of resources has to be defined in the terms of the contract. The political will needs to identify the force that has to implement the terms of the contract. What remains interesting about the social contract theory of Rousseau is that it is one that is revocable (Rousseau, 1947). The contract in question has to define the condition that determines the annulation of the contract. In this context, it is probable that skepticism and cynicism of most Cameroonians who reject harmonisation can be overcome. Unless the confidence of these terms is restored by the political will, harmonisation remains a difficult process in educational development in Cameroon.

Methodology of the study

There are two approaches of research in this study. These include; the quantitative and qualitative methods of research. The reason for these two methods lies in the fact that the weaknesses of one approach should be complemented by the strength of the other. The idea is that one can be more confident with a result if different methods lead to the same result. By combining multiple observers, theories, methods, and empirical materials, researchers can hope to overcome the weakness or intrinsic biases and the problems that come from single method, single-observer and single-theory studies. Triangulation is a powerful technique that facilitates validation of data through cross verification from two or more sources (Yin, 1984). In particular, it refers to the application and combination of several research methodologies in the study of the same phenomenon. For this quantitative method, the instrument was a questionnaire. The construction of a questionnaire was based on the main themes in the research questions. For qualitative approach, the instruments were interviews and focus group discussion guides for collecting data (Patton, 1990). A pilot test was carried out to test the validity of the main research instrument, the questionnaire. The pilot test proved that the instrument was reliable. This test also helped to modify some of the questions to avoid ambiguity. The sample regions for collection of data included the Centre and North-West regions. The target population included teachers, students and student-teachers in secondary schools and Higher Teacher Training Colleges for both general and technical education. The division of the scope is in two parts; viz, content and geographical delimitations. There are different categories gotten through purposive sampling. University lecturers, Teachers, pedagogic inspectors, student teachers and some students who provided responses to our questionnaire. Some of them were sampled for focus group discussions and interviews.

Findings

The presentation of the findings follow the two objectives highlighted at the initial stage of the paper. These objectives are analysed based on the opinions about the place of politics in two sub-systems of education. The domination of the English sub-system by the majority French sub-system is presented as a problem to educational development in Cameroon. Apart from that, divisions amongst Cameroonians on harmonisation betrays most problems of policy-making in the school system in Cameroon.

Political will and Domination from the Majority French

Table 1: Distribution of opinions on role of political will on domination from the majority French

	High	Important	Average	Low	Little or no influence	Indifferent	Total
Numbers	187	115	24	17	45	12	400
Percentage	46,8	28,8	6,0	4,3	11,3	3,0	100

Figure 1: Percentage Distribution of Opinions on domination from the majority French.

Table 1 expresses opinions on the domination from the French majority will. The results prove that domination from the majority will, which is the French sub-system of education is a weakness in policy-making towards educational development. To justify this result, from the 400 respondents, 187 which is 46.8%, say that it is a serious matter. For them, the domination is high. Also, 115, which is 28.8% hold that the domination is an important factor that influences educational growth. In addition, 24 respondents, which is 6% maintain that the problem is average. 17 respondents consider it to be low, that is, 4.3% and 45 of them see it as insignificant. This is 11%.

The responses that present this factor as low and insignificant represent negative answers to the problem in question. Those who say it is high, important and average affirm the problem as a barrier to educational development. This expression is done in different degrees. Therefore, the sum total of the affirmative responses is 326 giving us 75.6%. Those denying the problem make up 62, which constitute 15.6%. 12 respondents, which represent 3% remain indifferent by refusing to circle any of the options.

These statistics justify the hypothesis because the greater number of responses affirms the problem in question. This testifies the issues raised during many discussions. The domination of the French sub-system is discernable in attempts of assimilation arising in almost every discussion with teachers in the English sub-system of education. This is seemingly an important issue that requires attention. There seems to be mutual suspicion and distrust between the two sub-systems of education. One of the national pedagogic inspectors for the teaching of French language to the English speaking Cameroonians testifies that there is every reason for the English sub-system to have fear in the majority will, the French sub-system. He argues that there is a superiority complex and the intention to deceive under the guise of harmonisation. Going down memory lane, he highlights examples of promises and terms of contracts between the French and the English-speaking Cameroonians that have not been fulfilled. For instance, terms binding the federation in Cameroon have never been respected. This condition renders the problem more complicated. This calls for a reconsideration of many political options in Cameroon. The reason for this is justified in the negative impact political deception is having on education.

For the responses that deny the domination of the majority French, one thinks they arise from some respondents in the French speaking part of Cameroon. They do not see the domination. Though the percentage is low, it must be argued that these persons do not have the same experiences like the English speaking Cameroonians. Those who are indifferent may be persons with very little interest in political matters. They may not know much about Cameroonian politics and how this factor impedes educational development in the country. Finally, the confirmation of the problem as seen in the results justify why some English speaking Cameroonians think there is complicity between the political will and the French sub-system to destroy the English sub-system.

Division amongst Cameroonians on Harmonisation of Educational Values**Table 2: Distribution of opinions on divisions amongst Cameroonians on harmonisation**

	High	Important	Average	Low	Little or no	Indifferent	Total
Numbers	121	92	70	73	26	18	400
Percentage	30,3	23,0	17,5	18,3	6,5	4,5	100

Figure 2: Percentage Distribution of Opinions of Cameroonians on harmonisation

Table 2 shows how the attitudes of some English-speaking Cameroonians frustrate educational development. From the results, 121 respondents, which represent 30.3%, observe that this problem highly influences education. 92 respondents indicating 23% say it is an important factor. 70 of them, which makes 17.5% consider it as average. Although all these three categories of respondents confirm the problem, they do so in different degrees. 73 respondents deny the problem and say it is insignificant. This is 18.3%. 26 (6.5%) say it has no role to play in educational development and 18 (4.5%) sit on the fence.

As indicated above, 283 respondents confirm the problem. These respondents testify that there is a dividing attitude in some English-speaking Cameroonians. This attitude frustrates any vision in attempting to put in place policies for equal learning opportunities in the two sub-systems of education. In some of the discussions in Bamenda, one of the English speaking parts of Cameroon, this point comes up very frequently. Some teachers in English sub-system argue that harmonisation of the two sub-systems of education is superfluous. For them, the two sub-systems portray two different countries cohabiting in an unholy marriage. To use the words of one of the teachers: « *let no one put together what God has put asunder* » (Interviews with teachers in Bamenda, 12/10/2016).

At the initial stage of the research, some preliminary studies with some interviews and groups revealed these tendencies. Some teachers in the Anglophone sub-system dismissed the topic and considered it irrelevant. The reason advanced by one of the teachers is that this issue is a forgotten matter because better plans have been put in place to separate the country. This implied after separation, efforts towards harmonisation will be futile. These reactions portray the absence of openness. This reinforces the argument given by one of the vice principals for the French sub-system in Cameroon. He contends that Anglophones are hesitant to compromise any of their values. This uncompromising tendency is so strong and stands as one of the problems to be resolved while seeking to redefine the destiny of the educational system in Cameroon.

For respondents who deny the problem, perhaps they are unaware of some of the realities in Cameroonian politics. This problem must be redressed. For those indifferent, their political inclinations are primordial. For them, secessionist feeling is a non-event. In spite of all these, these results as presented in table 2 and figure 2 above confirm the hypothesis that the weak political will explain some problems in the educational system in Cameroon.

Political Will in the Educational Sub-systems

This sub-section examines the association between the political will in the country and some problems in the educational sub-systems. Two aspects studied under this sub-section are the implementation of policy and support of legal frameworks and the politics of unity and national integration. The point here is how these aspects of the political will influence the educational system of Cameroon.

Table 3. Association between Educational Development and the Support of Policy and Legal Frameworks

Policy and legal frameworks enacted are neither fully favourable to nor enhancing the growth of the English sub-system * educational growth exists in all sub-systems
Cross tabulation

Count

		Educational growth exists in all sub-systems				Total
		strongly agree	Agree	disagree	strongly disagree	
policy and legal frameworks enacted are neither fully favourable nor enhancing the growth of the English sub-system	High	21	9	35	77	142
	important	21	4	26	33	84
	Average	16	25	24	36	101
	Low	3	6	0	14	23
	little or no	7	5	4	5	21
Total		68	49	89	165	371

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	46,939 ^a	12	,000
Likelihood Ratio	51,568	12	,000
Linear-by-Linear Association	9,867	1	,002
N of Valid Cases	371		

a. 4 cells (20,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2,77.

The Chi Square probability above is 0.000. This result is less than 0.01 (1%). It denies the null hypothesis that educational growth of the two sub-systems of education and the policy and legal frameworks are independent. The implication is that there is a close relationship between the policy and legal frameworks with educational growth. Therefore, the problems of the educational system in Cameroon is rooted in the failure of the political will to enact, implement and support policies and legal frameworks that promote the two sub-systems in the country.

Table: 4 Association between Educational Objectives and Politics of Unity and National Integration

politics of unity and national integration exist * harmonisation exists in all aspects of education**Cross tabulation**

Count

		harmonisation exists in all aspects of education				Total
		strongly agree	Agree	disagree	strongly disagree	
politics of unity and national integration exist	High	37	9	29	36	111
	Important	12	14	19	32	77
	Average	11	10	23	41	85
	Low	11	6	17	30	64
	little or no	9	0	6	26	41
Total		80	39	94	165	378

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	31,249 ^a	12	,002
Likelihood Ratio	34,215	12	,001
Linear-by-Linear Association	11,445	1	,001
N of Valid Cases	378		

a. 1 cells (5,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4,23.

The Chi Square probability is 0.002, which is less than 5.0%. This result rejects the null hypothesis that harmonisation and the politics of unity and national integration are independent. There is a strong correlation between these two variables. This argument is justified by the fact that lack of harmonisation in the school systems compromises the policy of unity and national integration. Therefore, the vision of unity, which the political will stands to promote is enhanced by harmonisation of the educational sub-systems in Cameroon.

From the results obtained, there is a strong correlation between the political will and the policy of harmonisation. This association testifies the fact that the absence of a strong political will is responsible for divisions amongst Cameroonians on harmonization of educational values. Therefore, the second hypothesis is confirmed. It states that the absence of a strong political will prevents the implementation of the policy of harmonisation and the realisation of the politics of unity and national integration in the educational system.

Discussions

In the discussions, two main issues corresponding to the specific objectives of the study are examined. These include the domination of the French will in the school system of education and the reaction of the political will on the division of Cameroonians on the subject of harmonising educational values.

Political will and the Domination of French

In Cameroon, schools are not seen as treating students from the two sub-systems of education with equality. The question of fairness in the educational system is a sensitive issue following Dewey's democratic theory of education. This is because policy-making render most schools responsible for educational inequalities. Considering that the causes for inequalities are political, economic or socio-cultural, there is an underlying role of the political will. Precisely, the problem stems from the distribution of educational assets to the

various regions in the country. The respect for human rights is seemingly not primordial in determining this distribution. Democratic education emphasizes equal access of all persons to quality education. This does not necessarily refer to the same values of education and the same examination board, but simply extends to the provision of educational facilities and resources that enhance the aptitude and interests of all persons according to their needs (Dewey, 1966).

The first problem of domination is discernable in the subtle “francophonisation” of the English sub-system of education. This aspect is very dominant in the interview responses given by Anglophones with regard to the management of technical education by the *baccalaureat* office. At this juncture, one wonders why the examination boards of the English sub-system of technical education was suppressed in favour of the French examination board. One may be tempted to say these were efforts towards harmonisation. Far from it, it is an incarnation of assimilation. The process of harmonisation is contractual and not imposing. The Anglophones argue that “*there is a need for an immediate stoppage of Certificat d’Aptitude Professionnelle (CAP), Probatoire Technique and Baccalaureat Technique from the English sub-system of education.*” “*There is a subtle francophonisation of the Anglophones in Cameroon in the guise of harmonisation*” (Interviews with representatives of Anglophone Trade Unions on 20/11/2016). With respect to the opinions of Anglophones, one finds an educational policy that fuels the domination of the English sub-system by the French sub-system. Most of these respondents argue that the frustration of technical education in the English part of the country is rooted in harmonisation as an educational objective. Following their arguments, there is a need to have an independent technical examination board for the English-speaking Cameroonians to limit school drop-outs and poor management of examinations.

The second problem stems from the excessive deployment of francophones as teachers in the English sub-system of education. This problem is linked to poor management of human resources in the school system. The matter at stake is not limited to the deployment, but that the francophones do not have the adequate language proficiency to teach in English. Considering the power of language in the communication of knowledge, this problem cannot be over-emphasized (Fonlon, 1963). Most of these teachers teach in French while others do so in pigin. For the Anglophones, this is a subtle attempt to destroy the English sub-system of education. For some Anglophones, the language these teachers use to teach the mis neither French, nor English nor Pigin. It is another reality in the midst of these languages. These render learning boring and thus a high drop-out of students from schools. To combat this problem, the Anglophones observe that *we need a withdrawal of all francophones posted to teach Anglophone children and a redeployment of Anglophone teachers sent to Francophone colleges*” (Interviews with Representatives of Anglophone Trade Unions on 20/11/2016).

Still within the framework of discussions with the representatives of the trade Unions in the English sub-system of education, most of them argue that

(...) on 15th, December 2015, we requested for the withdrawal and re-posting of all French speaking teachers from Anglophone classrooms except bilingual teachers and those posted as lecturers and administrators in the Universities of Buea and Bamenda.

This request made by the teachers in the English sub-system of education was given a deaf ear. In this context, one may be tempted to exploit the multicultural theory of education to condemn lack of recognition and tolerance on the part of Anglophones in this request. At the same time, the problem of language is not a light matter. Drawing inspiration from Bernard Fonlon (1963), a Cameroonian philosopher of language education, the importance of teaching in a language one masters best cannot be over-emphasized. Language is a tool of communication and the desire to provide jobs and positions for loved ones should not compromise this requirement. On this account, the request of Anglophones has both a theoretical and a philosophical justifications. This is not a light matter to be given a deafening ear.

In the third place, the numerical domination of francophones in schools meant to train teachers for the Anglophone school system is appalling. This domination comes under the policy of regional balance. In most competitive examinations, regional balance is very outstanding in the admissions of students in the Higher (Technical) Teacher Training Colleges of Bamenda and Buea, hosting the English sub-system whereas in other areas regional balance is a nightmare.

There is a need for transparency in the management of admissions into medical and other professional schools in the Universities of Buea and Bamenda, where Anglophone students are numerically marginalized and where the heroes of Cameroon General Certificate of Examinations (GCE) have no place. Decisions launching recruitment into HTTTC Bambili and Kumba are still open to Francophones to the near total exclusion of Anglophones.

Highlighting the above opinion of Anglophones, one maintains that most problems encountered by the English sub-system of education are rooted in the political will. For some Anglophone intellectuals, this is a deliberate action to destabilize and destroy the English sub-system of education. The political will has to be convincing in justifying this issue to the contrary. With the democratic theory of John Dewey, all persons are expected to have equal privileges, opportunities and chances to develop their potentials in order to contribute to the development of the community. The experience of the Anglophones in the school system in Cameroon is contrary to these commendable values of democratic education. In this case, lack of tolerance, recognition of the other and acceptance, values akin to multicultural education are neglected in the management of school affairs.

Lastly, the infrastructure put in place and provision of personnel have to take into consideration the needs and interests of the Anglophones. Fairness in the provision of these facilities in the different regions can be examined from over-crowded classrooms and poor staffing ratios. This disgusting experience lies in the fact that most teachers in some schools are probationers or disillusioned “old hands”. This is discernable in situations where some schools embark on profit maximization rather than quality education. Badly equipped schools are also in their numbers with ill-repute. For Dewey’s democratic theory of education, school systems are reflections of the values promoted in the society. If one wants to establish a democratic society, one has to develop democratic values in schools. Owing to Dewey, the problems highlighted in the findings by both Anglophones and francophones betray lack of tolerance, prejudices and mutual respect.

In a nutshell, four major issues have been highlighted to portray how the political will fuels the domination of the French sub-system of education in Cameroon. These included the « francophonisation » of the English sub-system, the excessive deployment of francophones into Anglosaxon schools as teachers, lecturers and administrators, the numerical domination of francophones in Higher Teacher Training Colleges and Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges of Bamenda and Kumba and, the poor infrastructure and staffing ratios that do not meet the needs of the people.

Reaction of Political will to Division amongst Cameroonians on Harmonisation

Harmonisation stands as a subject of controversy between the Anglophones and the francophones. The semantic problem here is rooted in narrow-mindedness and egoism rather than the concept itself. The saying goes that « abuse does not take away use ». Lack of harmonisation in the two school systems portray problems of quality and equity in the official school programmes. These problems tend to compromise the process for peace building and encourage clashes of colonial cultures in the school system. The main problem with harmonisation comes from mutual suspicion and distrust between Anglophones and Francophones. According to the findings, this lack of trust is rooted in the deceptive practices of policy-making in the different spheres of governance in the country.

Considering the domination of the French sub-system in Cameroon, the question of harmonisation and lack of trust prompt most responses to refer to assimilation. This is seemingly an important issue that requires attention. There is mutual suspicion and distrust between the two sub-systems of education. As testified in the findings, one of the national pedagogic inspectors for the teaching of French language to the English speaking Cameroonians explains every reason for the English sub-system to have fear in the majority will, the French sub-system. For him, a superiority complex and the intention to deceive under the guise of harmonisation is the objective of the dominant French sub-system of education. Going down memory lane, he highlights examples of promises and terms of contracts between the French and the English-speaking Cameroonians that have not been fulfilled. For instance, terms binding the federation in Cameroon were never respected. With this opinion, one wonders how the political will could manipulate terms of contracts and laws in favour of one sub-system to the relative neglect of the other (Ngalim, 2014c). This calls for a reconsideration of many policies in order to repair the negative impact political deception is having on education.

Drawing from the Marxist conflict theory, which describes the tension between the bourgeoisie (stronger force of capitalism) and the proletariat (the working class and weaker force), one is able to explain the tension that exist between francophones (the stronger force) and Anglophones (the weaker minority) in Cameroon. From the findings, the stronger party emphasizes its own values to the relative neglect of the values of the Anglophone minority in the school system. As far as the provision of educational rights, privileges and opportunities are concerned, the Anglophone minority complains of injustice, marginalisation and the attempt to francophonize Anglophones in Cameroon. This leads Anglophones to preserve some prejudices about francophones and to constantly hesitate to dialogue amicably.

The diversity experienced from the two-fold colonial heritage in the educational system constitute sources of prejudices, narrow-mindedness, discrimination and lack of respect. Educational equity is a mandated right to all students in democratic education. This entails equal access to classes, facilities and educational programmes irrespective of one's region of origin, tribe, gender, sexual orientation, disabilities, first language or other distinguishing characteristics (Ngalim, 2014b). In upholding educational equity in Cameroon, schools in all parts of the country are required to provide certain programmes for students to ensure equal education.

One major problem arising from the domination of the French sub-system is the inequities that continue to exist amongst schools. It is evident that inequities are prevalent in every society. Anything that makes two people different becomes a big challenge to society. This is not how things go on in this period of time. Discrimination is a noun that is not discreetly used and differences have become a source of isolation. It is quite disappointing that these inequities are rampant in academic institutions where students are expected to learn commendable values. Schools are expected to be venues where young people experience the principle of compromise and equality. The responsibility of the government to fight discrimination in education is outstanding. However, in Cameroon, it is still true that a different sub-system of education may mean less chances of a better education, less opportunity and a reduced potential for greatness (Ngalim, 2014c). From this premise, it follows that students have not got an equal access to learn in the educational sub-systems in Cameroon. Everyone is not prioritized in the distinct sub-systems. The problem one has to raise is whether a sub-system of education is an indicator of educational potential or of people who work hard. This is the debate proposed by this research for policy-makers to consider.

Besides, discrimination is still prominent in the different aspects of education in Cameroon. Physical differences are easy to identify because ignorance and prejudices characterize our schools. The argument to be maintained here is that there is no relation between one's place of origin, cultural background and one's aptitude to education. It is the place of schools to address these issues as it greatly affects the students both in academic and social lives. The process of harmonisation promises a means towards limiting these problems. Inequality in education is one of the leading reasons for the dropout rate in both general and technical schools. The students from the two sub-systems are not given equal opportunities. It is a regrettable fact that some students are learning a lot more than others because their schools have more qualified teachers and better facilities. It is therefore important to challenge the political will that entertains inequities in schools so that they could seek remedies to these problems.

Another question arising from the political reaction to division of Cameroonians on harmonisation is equity and excellence in Mathematics for the two sub-systems of education. The argument here goes that narrowing the gap of educational inequity through politics like implementing the educational objective of harmonisation in good faith entails a great success. In this case, all students regardless of tribe, ethnic group, gender, socio-economic status, geographic location, age, language, disability or prior Mathematical learning and achievement will be given equal access to Mathematical excellence. The concept of equity has profound implications for teaching and learning Mathematics through-out the school community. The assurance of equity and excellence has to be at the core of systematic reform efforts in harmonising the educational sub-systems in Cameroon.

The case at hand refers to most students including a disproportionate number of Anglophone minorities who leave school without the Mathematical skills they need to thrive in an increasingly complex global economy. All students can learn a significant core of Mathematics and that the entire school community must have high expectations for every child's education (Nelson, Palonsky & McCarthy, 2006 p.34). The poor dispositions of most students from the English sub-system in Mathematics as compared to their counterparts in the French Sub-system require a critical consideration by policy-makers with regard to

the provision of adequate personnel and material resources. Culture and linguistic diversity do not justify discrepancies in academic standards. In a bid to increase the participation and success of under-presented groups, the arguments upholding a harmonised curriculum require great attention from the body politic.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The role of the political will in educational development has been examined in this paper from the perspective of weaknesses in policy-making. The weaknesses of the political will is discerned in its complicity to the French domination of the English sub-system of education and its inability to convincingly establish the educational objective of harmonisation to meet the politics of unity and national integration in Cameroon. This article set out to summon the political will to revisit policy-making considering values of a multicultural democratic education in order to ensure educational development in the country. Given the issues raised in the findings and the discussions, some recommendations have been made.

First, there is need for a control mechanism to ensure the implementation of policies following the contract of equal status in education. A contract is said to be an agreement between two equals. Equal here refers to the availability of the same opportunities, privileges and resources to all parties. The principle of fairness requires the recognition of the contracting parties and the respect of the terms of the contract as stated at the time of the contract. This contract needs to be one of the steps towards harmonisation. Prior to harmonisation, the terms of the contract should be clearly spelt out. This contract must be revocable in case one of the contracting parties fails to keep to the terms.

Secondly, in the informal setting, exchanges amongst teachers from the different sub-systems should be encouraged through cooperative learning values. Let us take the merits of assignments carried out in pedagogic seminars and exchanges between teachers. The lesson to be maintained here is the value of dialogue and that no one frame of interpreting the truth is more important than the other. Everyone deserves to be heard and be understood.

Harmonisation of the educational system is a gradual but necessary process to be carried out in good faith. It is not assimilation and the abuse and fear of harmonisation does not render it evil. It is simply narrow-mindedness and lack of openness to growth. Each sub-system can still maintain its autonomy within the framework of harmonisation. This is an aspect that policy-makers have to put in place, whereby they precisely mean what they say and say what they mean.

Language proficiency and cultural pluralism should be given recognition and great attention in policy-making on school matters ranging from the curricular development, recruitment and deployment of teacher to schools and appointments of administrators.

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